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EXAMINING THE DYNAMICS OF CASHEW KERNEL EXPORTS IN TANZANIA: A TIME SERIES FORECASTING APPROACH

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ABSTRACT

This paper provides a comprehensive analysis of the future outlook for cashew kernel exports from Tanzania using an ARIMA (1,1,1) model based on 59 years of time series data. The study highlights the underutilization of Tanzania's cashew processing capacity and its impact on export growth, with forecasts showing minimal increases in kernel exports through 2033. The paper underscores the need for strategic planning and investment in processing infrastructure, technology, and capacity building to enhance the cashew industry's value addition and economic gains. The findings offer valuable insights for policymakers, investors, and industry stakeholders to formulate effective strategies and policies. The use of robust statistical modeling provides a reliable forecast, making this study a significant contribution to the field of agricultural economics and industrial development. The recommendations for enhancing the cashew value chain are particularly pertinent for maximizing Tanzania's economic benefits from its substantial raw cashew nut production.

Keywords: ARIMA, Cashew Kernel, Exports, Forecasting

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1. INTRODUCTION

Exports represent a crucial economic factor essential for fostering the economic advancement of any nation. These exports include products, services, and capital assets generated domestically and traded with foreign countries.

Raw cashew nuts (RCN) are among Tanzania's top export commodities, playing a crucial role in the agricultural sector and contributing to foreign exchange earnings. RCN exports realized around 520.4 Billion Tanzanian shillings in 2022 and ranked first in cash crop exports [1]. The Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) for Tanzania cashew kernel exports in the last 10 years is approximately -0.3385%, indicating a slight decrease in the export quantities of kernels. The country's RCN production is on the rise, and the failure to prioritize RCN processing within the country means that the country is missing out on the unrealized potential gains that come from cashew value addition. With the increase in Tanzania's raw cashew nuts production, the global cashew kernel demand, and the need to foster sustainable growth in the nation's export of kernels, it is imperative to understand the anticipated performance of the industry in the coming years.

Various forecasting techniques are used for predicting future events based on relevant variables with known past values [2]. It is crucial for governments, organizations, and decision-makers nowadays. Forecasting helps in anticipating future scenarios, mitigating risks, and taking advantage of new opportunities in a highly competitive and complex environment.

This study explored the future outlook of kernel exports in Tanzania using annual historical data from 1965 to 2023. An Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) model is employed to investigate the forecasting patterns of kernel exports. ARIMA models offer a strong framework for time series analysis and forecasting across a wide range of activities, for instance, in forecasting wheat production in India by [3], in crop yield forecasting in India by [4], forecasting cotton lint exports in Nigeria by [2], evaluating forecast performance of Malaysian goods export by [5], forecasting agricultural imports in Iraq [6], forecasting Indonesian coffee exports [7], and in forecasting the value of oil and gas exports in Indonesia by [8]. These studies collectively demonstrate the versatility and robustness of ARIMA models in forecasting, highlighting their importance in strategic economic planning and decision-making across different sectors.

2. METHODS

This study used secondary data for the years spanning 1965 to 2023, sourced from the FAOSTAT database and various published documents. The data has 59 observations sufficient for time series analysis and contains annual cashew kernel export quantities measured in metric tons.

2.1. Method of data analysis

This study used the ARIMA forecasting technique to analyze the collected data.

2.2. Model specification

An ARMA model combines both autoregressive (AR) and moving average (MA) components, often reflecting characteristics of both AR and MA processes within the time-series variable (Y). It is labeled as ARMA based on its capacity to capture these features. In an ARMA (p, q) process, there are typically p autoregressive terms and q moving average terms. This assumption holds under the condition that the time series under examination should exhibit stationarity. Nevertheless, most economic time series are non-stationary, meaning they possess a unit root. As a result, researchers need to difference the original time series' d' times to turn it stationary before applying the ARMA model. Hence, the original time series is labeled as

ARIMA (p,d,q), representing an autoregressive integrated moving average time series. Here, 'p' signifies the count of autoregressive terms, 'd' indicates the number of differencing iterations needed to achieve stationarity, and 'q' denotes the quantity of moving average terms.

ARIMA models are constructed using the Box-Jenkins methodology, which involves four key steps: identification, estimation, diagnostic checking, and forecasting. This iterative process optimizes model accuracy and reliability. Model identification involves checking if the time series data exhibits trend, seasonality, or stationarity. This step involves plotting the data, examining autocorrelation and partial autocorrelation functions, and determining whether differencing is necessary to achieve stationarity. Further, it involved determining the orders (p, d, and q) of the AR, I, and MA components within the model. The following step involved estimation. After determining the suitable values of p and q, the parameters associated with the autoregressive and moving average terms within the model are identified. After parameter estimation, diagnostic checking was performed to assess the adequacy of the model, which includes analyzing residuals to ensure they are not autocorrelated and exhibit constant variance over time. Once the model was validated through diagnostic checks, it was used to predict future values.

3. ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

An ARIMA model was used to forecast Tanzania kernel exports using the Box-Jenkins methodology.

3.1. Testing for stationarity

Before applying ARIMA, it is essential to verify whether the data is stationary or non-stationary. This study used the ADF test to assess the series' stationarity. The null hypothesis in this context is framed as the presence of a unit root or non-stationarity, as opposed to stationarity. TABLE 1 presents the outcome of the ADF test that was conducted. The P value of 0.1967 indicates that the original series is non-stationary but achieves stationarity after the first difference (d = 1), as shown in Fig 1. Consequently, the resulting differenced series is chosen for the implementation of ARIMA.

Table 1: Testing for stationarity

ADF	Probability	Test statistic
Original series	0.1967	-2.9359
First differenced series	< 0.0001	-4.4848

Figure 1: Plot of the stationary series

3.2. Model Identification

Based on the ACF plot of the stationary series, it is evident that the series remains stationary up to lag 1, implying that q equals 1. Similarly, according to the PACF plot of the stationary series, it remains stationary up to lag 2, indicating that p equals 2 (Fig 2). Therefore, the ARIMA model was provisionally configured as ARIMA (2,1,1). The plots also show the potential for the following ARIMA combinations: ARIMA (2,1,0), ARIMA (1,1,1), and ARIMA (1,1,0).

Figure 2: ACF and PACF plots of the stationary series

3.3. Model Estimation

Once the ARIMA model has been identified, the next step involves estimating the parameter coefficients. An optimal model is required to have the highest value of log-likelihood. It should also have lower values of AIC and BIC (signifying better model fit). As shown in TABLE 2, ARIMA (1,1,1) was determined to be the optimal model for forecasting kernel exports in Tanzania, with an AIC value of AIC and BIC values (1073.687) and (1081.842), respectively. The model also has the highest log-likelihood (-533.84) compared to other models. Therefore, this suggests that ARIMA (1,1,1) stands out as the most favorable model among the options explored.

Table 2: Parameter Estimation for Arima Models

ARIMA(p,d,q)	AR(1)	AR(2)	MA(1)	AIC	BIC	Log-Likelihood
2,1,1	-0.4144	-0.2484	-0.107	1077.857	1090.09	-534.93
1,1,1	0.4095		-0.9999	1073.687	1081.842	-533.84
2,1,0	-0.5121	-0.2872		1075.898	1084.053	-534.95
1,1,0	-0.39421			1079.018	1083.096	-537.51

3.4. Residual Analysis

Residual analysis was performed to assess whether residuals were not autocorrelated and exhibited constant variance over time.

Fig 3 shows that most values are concentrated around zero, and the residual series has a constant variance, indicating that it follows the white noise process. The residual ACFs and PACFs for the ARIMA (1,1,1), spanning from lag 1 to lag 19, all fall within the significance limits. Therefore, based on the ACF and PACF analyses, it can be concluded that there are no autocorrelations observed in the residuals between lag 1 and lag 19 within the fitted ARIMA (1,1,1) model.

Figure 3: Residual series plot, ACF plot of the residuals from ARIMA (1,1,1)

3.5. Forecasting

It was observed that the predicted exports from the ARIMA (1,1,1) have a CAGR of 2.72 (TABLE 3). Over the forecasted years, the annual growth rates tend to be extremely low, decreasing and approaching zero.

S/N	Year	Kernel Export (MT)	Annual Growth Rate (%)
1	2024	2930.114	
2	2025	2977.511	1.62
3	2026	2996.92	0.65
4	2027	3004.868	0.27
5	2028	3008.123	0.11
6	2029	3009.456	0.04
7	2030	3010.002	0.02
8	2031	3010.225	0.01
9	2032	3010.317	0.00
10	2033	3010.354	0.00
CAGR (%)			2.72

Table 3: 10-year forecasted values of Kernel exports

The forecasted data was plotted as shown in Fig 4, with the black line representing the original time series data, while the blue line represents the predicted data.

Figure 4: Forecasts of Tanzania kernel exports from ARIMA (1,1,1)

4. CONCLUSION

This study used ARIMA (1,1,1) to predict kernel exports from Tanzania using historical data. Over the forecasted years, the annual growth rates of kernel exports tend to be extremely low, approaching zero. The prediction for 2033 resulted in approximately 3010.354 tonnes, which is an insignificant increase from the preceding forecasted amounts. The country's cashew processing capacity is underutilized, resulting in low exports of cashew kernels. Based on the predicted kernel exports, industrial development agencies, policymakers, investors, and other industry stakeholders can make strategic plans to improve the country's cashew processing activities. The government might also consider formulating policies aiming at enhancing all stages of the cashew value chain. It demands continuous and huge investment in processing infrastructure, technology, and capacity building to unlock the full potential of Tanzania's cashew industry and maximize its economic benefits.

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